

Sedimentation Risk Index (SRI) Manual for Stream Crossing Assessment

Original Developed By
THREE RIVERS RESOURCE CONSERVATION & DEVELOPMENT COUNCIL'S
SRI Manual for Stream Crossing Assessment

ALABAMA RIVER AND STREAMS NETWORK

September 2021

SRI MANUAL FOR STREAM CROSSING ASSESSMENT

Contacts

U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Alabama Ecological Service Office
1208 Main Street
Daphne AL 36526
Phone: 251-441-5181

Geological Survey of Alabama
420 Hackberry Lane
Tuscaloosa, AL 35401
Phone: 205-349-2852

For more information, please go to: <http://www.alh2o.org/>
To access the interactive mapper, please go to: <https://warcapps.usgs.gov/SHU/Map>

PREFACE

This guide was prepared as a practical manual for personnel involved in paved and unpaved road-stream crossing assessment wishing to use the Sedimentation Risk Index (SRI). Minimal experience is required, but some knowledge or experience with erosion and stream morphology may be beneficial.

The contents of this field guide were derived from “Development and Use of a Sedimentation Risk Index for Unpaved Road-Stream Crossings in the Choctawhatchee Watershed” (Witmer et al., 2009), the Northwest Florida Unpaved Road-Stream Crossing Manual (U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, 2005), and the Recommended Practices Manual: A Guideline for Maintenance and Service of Unpaved Roads (Choctawhatchee, Pea, and Yellow Rivers Watershed Management Authority, 2000).

This guide is intended as a field supplement, not a replacement, for pre-existing literature for stream crossings. Due to the brevity required of a compact manual useful for field work, extensive background information and best management practices related to paved and unpaved road concerns have not been included. Consult the literature above or other sources for more extensive information not included in this guide.

HOW DO I USE THIS GUIDE?

Included in the back of this guide is a sample Sedimentation Risk Index (SRI) datasheet (see Appendix A). The sections of this manual are arranged in the same order as they appear in that datasheet. You may wish to omit some sections or create your own customized data entry method. However, the guidelines that follow assume you have used, or are familiar with, the included format.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Preface	iii
How Do I Use This Guide?	iii
Table of Contents	iv
Introduction	1
What Is The Sedimentation Risk Index (SRI)?.....	2
How Can The SRI Be Applied.....	4
Why Use the SRI in Stream Crossing Projects?.....	4
Baseline	5
Waterway	9
Least-Impacted Channel Morphology.....	10
Moderately-Impacted Channel Morphology.....	12
Most-Impacted Channel Morphology.....	13
Downstream Channel/Bank Alteration.....	15
Classifying Dry Channels.....	17
Completing The Waterway Survey.....	18
Crossing Structure	19
Measuring Crossing Structure Dimensions.....	22
Scoring Crossing Conditions.....	25
Completing The Crossing Structure Survey.....	30
Road Approaches I	31
Scoring Road Approaches I.....	33
Completing The Road Approaches I Survey.....	35
Photopoints	36
Example of Photos Needed for the SRI Datasheet.....	37

Road Approaches II	39
SRI Score	44
Literature cited	45
Appendix A: SRI Datasheet	46
Appendix B: Rosgen Stream Types	48
Appendix C: Road Angle and Percent Slope	49
Appendix D: Equipment List	50

Introduction

Stream crossing practices are site specific and involve multi-factorial considerations.

Paved and unpaved road-stream crossings (SCs) present both economic and environmental costs to counties and local municipalities, and often lead to additional burdens being placed on state and federal agencies. Many of the costs associated with SCs are directly related to erosion.

- Maintaining passable roadways
- Maintaining drainage system integrity
- Flood prevention or recovery
- Stream and/or waterway navigation
- Loss of biota, riparian zones, or other natural resources
- Loss of aesthetics or recreational use

SC practices should be selectively applied to maintain the utility and integrity of the road system and to minimize environmental impacts. These practices must consider the following characteristics.

- SC practices should be based on scientific studies and testing, and be applied using best professional judgment for the situation.
- SC practices are site specific and involve multi-factorial considerations. The application and effectiveness of SC practices may vary significantly depending on the protocol or conditions.
- SC practices will unlikely reduce all roadway and drainage erosion, but should minimize environmental impacts.
- Assumptions are made on the effectiveness of SC practices prescribed, with risk and responsibility falling upon that of the project implementers.
- SC practices are not “build and walk away” plans, and should involve some form of post-implementation monitoring and maintenance.
- SC practices require a site-specific understanding of natural and anthropogenic influences before prescribing a project plan.

Limited budgets make evaluating and prioritizing SCs a means for efficient sedimentation abatement. Risk assessment of SCs must also be approached from many angles. There are a number of different tools and approaches to determining the quality and conditions of SCs. This guide, however, was written specifically to aid personnel in using the Sediment Risk Index (SRI) to evaluate stream crossings. The use of the SRI does not preclude other forms of site assessment, and a combination of tools is encouraged.

WHAT IS THE SEDIMENTATION RISK INDEX (SRI)?

The SRI was developed as a model for prioritizing SCs in the Choctawhatchee watershed within

southeast Alabama from 2006 to 2007. Over seventy-three variables were collected from SCs including information on waterway conditions, crossing structures, road approaches, and roadside soil erosion features that promote sediment delivery.

These findings were summarized into a 12-metric index (the SRI), modeled after Karr's Index of Biotic Integrity (IBI) for fish and other assemblages (Karr, 1981). The goal of condensing SC data into an index was to reduce the time and manpower investment of collecting data.

FIGURE 1.1 SURVEYED SITES IN THE CHOCTAWHATCHEE WATERSHED OF SOUTHEAST ALABAMA

Each metric of the SRI is standardized with scores 1 (most-impacted), 3 (moderately-impacted), or 5 (least-impacted) (Stewart et al., 2006) The scores for the 12 metrics are summed into a single SRI value ranging from 12 to 60, which is used for determining site rank and condition.

We are now applying the SRI across the state of Alabama and in surrounding states at high priority restoration areas referred to as Strategic Habitat AND River Reach Units (SHU and SRRU) (Figure 1.2).

Strategic Habitat and River Reach Units for Aquatic Species of Conservation Concern in Alabama and Adjoining States

Berry H. (Nick) Tew, Jr.
State Geologist

by
E. Anne Wynn, Patrick E. O'Neil, Stuart W. McGregor - Geological Survey of Alabama; Jeffrey R. Powell, Jennifer P. Grunewald, Anthony D. Ford - United States Fish and Wildlife Service; Paul D. Johnson and Jeffrey T. Garner - Alabama Department of Conservation and Natural Resources

The Alabama Rivers and Streams Network has designated 46 watershed areas and 14 river and stream reaches in Alabama and neighboring states to focus management, recovery, and restoration activities for populations of rare fishes, mussels, snails, and crayfishes. These Strategic Habitat Units (SHUs) and Strategic River Reach Units (SRRUs) were selected based on the presence of federally listed (under the Endangered Species Act) and state imperiled species, essential habitat components required by these species to survive, and the vulnerability of these habitats to potential threats. The SHUs and SRRUs include a substantial part

of Alabama's remaining high-quality water courses and reflect the variety of aquatic habitats occupied by these species historically and presently. The map below displays the locations of the 46 SHUs and 14 SRRUs in Alabama and adjoining states. Colored polygons represent the watershed area of each SHU, with the exception of the Mobile-Tensaw River Delta SHU, which drains the entire Mobile River basin. Each SRRU represents the corridor of a major river or large stream. Each SHU and SRRU is also part of a larger National Hydrography Dataset (NHD) Hydrologic Unit (HU)-4 subregion. The index map displays the location of each HU-4 subregion.

Alabama Rivers and Streams Network
www.arsn20.org

Hydrologic Unit (HU)-4 subregions in Alabama and adjoining states.

HU-4 Code	HU-4 name	Index map unit
0003	Middle Tennessee - Elk	1
0316	Mobiles - Tombigbee	2
0315	Alabama	3
0314	Chattahoochee - Escambia	4
0313	Apalachicola	5

Strategic Habitat Units (SHUs) and Strategic River Reach Units (SRRUs) in Alabama and adjoining states.

Map No.	Watershed or river reach name	SHU (SRRU)	HU-4	Index map unit
1	Boat Creek	X	1	1
2	Tennessee River downstream of Wilson Dam	X	1	1
3	Cypress Creek	X	1	1
4	Shoal Creek	X	1	1
5	Elk River	X	1	1
6	Limestone Creek	X	1	1
7	Tennessee River downstream of Gantersville Dam	X	1	1
8	Fruit River	X	1	1
9	Pain River	X	1	1
10	Tennessee River downstream of Nickajack Dam	X	1	1
11	Lower Tombigbee River	X	2	2
12	Susannah River	X	2	2
13	Traveler Creek	X	2	2
14	Sippey River	X	2	2
15	Lubbet Creek	X	2	2
16	Coaffle Creek	X	2	2
17	Lougalla Creek	X	2	2
18	Butcherhook River	X	2	2
19	East Fork Tombigbee River	X	2	2
20	Bull Mountain Creek	X	2	2
21	Trout River	X	2	2
22	Upper Spooky Fork	X	2	2
23	Lower Fork	X	2	2
24	Lower Alabama River	X	3	3
25	Big Flat Creek	X	3	3
26	Bogue Chitto Creek	X	3	3
27	Cahaba River	X	3	3
28	Coosa River downstream of Jordan Dam	X	3	3
29	Hatchet Creek	X	3	3
30	Yelloweef Creek	X	3	3
31	Coosa River downstream of Logan Martin Dam	X	3	3
32	Folly Creek	X	3	3
33	Lower Chattahoochee Creek	X	3	3
34	Chesha Creek	X	3	3
35	Shoal Creek	X	3	3
36	Big Canoe Creek	X	3	3
37	White Lake bypass (Old Coosa River)	X	3	3
38	Terrapin Creek	X	3	3
39	Oostanaula River	X	3	3
40	Uphatchoo Creek	X	3	3
41	Upper Tallapoosa River	X	3	3
42	Concun - Escambia River	X	4	4
43	Yonder Creek	X	4	4
44	Arroyo Mill Creek	X	4	4
45	Pier Run Creek	X	4	4
46	Lower Pine River	X	4	4
47	Upper Pine River	X	4	4
48	Lower Chattahoochee River	X	4	4
49	West Fork Chattahoochee River	X	4	4
50	Flat Creek	X	4	4
51	Limestone Creek	X	4	4
52	Wright Creek	X	4	4
53	Steele Creek	X	4	4
54	Holmes Creek	X	4	4
55	Econfine Creek	X	4	4
56	Yonah River	X	4	4
57	Upper Chipola River	X	5	5
58	Little Creek	X	5	5
59	Lower Chipola River	X	5	5

Published by Geological Survey of Alabama, 2018

FIGURE 1.2. MAP OF THE STRATEGIC HABITAT AND RIVER REACH UNITS IN ALABAMA AND SURROUNDING STATES (SPECIAL MAP 248-B, 2018).

HOW CAN THE SRI BE APPLIED TO STREAM CROSSING PROJECTS?

The SRI may be used within the context of watershed management plans to create a priority listing of SCs and focus resources on the most impacted sites. The SRI may also be used in conjunction with other data collection methods to create comprehensive monitoring plans. Site evaluations with the SRI can also be used independently to target SCs, gauge BMPs, or assess trends.

FIGURE 2.1. SAMPLE BOXPLOT OF BEST 10 AND WORST 10 SITES EVALUATED WITH THE SRI

WHY USE THE SRI IN STREAM CROSSING PROJECTS?

- The cost effectiveness of the SRI is that it requires a minimal amount of manpower, time, and equipment to collect useful data. Refer to Appendix B for a recommended list of equipment.
- The usability of the SRI allows personnel with minimal experience to collect useful data.
- The science behind the SRI results in scores that were standardized based on previously collected statistical data and peer-reviewed study.
- The relevancy of the SRI is that low scores indicate problematic sites due to low stream channel stability, improper crossing structure installation, or road approach sediment contribution.

Baseline

Crossing ID's should be acquired from the Service, Alabama Ecological Service Field office prior to field work.

The Baseline section of the SRI refers to metadata pertaining to the site, such as the date the SC was surveyed and what personnel collected data. The baseline data is extremely important for the associated SRI database and web mapper (currently being developed for the Alabama Rivers and Stream Network).

SHU Name:				SHU #:		Visible Threats (check as many as applicable)			
Crossing ID: (FIPS# - Crossing #) _____ - _____						Livestock access <input type="checkbox"/>			
Date:		Time 24hr: Start		End		Eroding banks <input type="checkbox"/>			
Road Name:				Upland		Fish barriers <input type="checkbox"/>			
Stream Name:				Lowland		Road material in stream <input type="checkbox"/>			
Surveyor(s):				New Crossing? <input type="checkbox"/>		ATV access <input type="checkbox"/>			
State:		County:		Owner of GPS, camera: Note taker:		No riparian cover <input type="checkbox"/>			
Latitude (DD):						No visible threats <input type="checkbox"/>			
Longitude(DD):						Others:			
Road Type: Paved Unpaved		Public Private		Qualitative Sed Risk Level (circle one): LOW MODERATE HIGH Unsure					
Full Survey Performed? Yes No		If No, why not?				Restoration			
Other Comments:						Project Possibility (circle one):			
						Yes		No	

FIGURE 3.1. BASELINE SECTION OF THE SRI DATASHEET

Note: If a landowner provides contact information do not write the information on the datasheet. Record this information elsewhere, like a field notebook, and keep it with the datasheets.

The **SHU Name** and **SHU #** are associated with the Strategic Habitat Units created by the Alabama Rivers and Stream Network. Strategic Habitat Units are selected watersheds and river segments in Alabama, and surrounding states, that focus conservation activities for managing, recovering and restoring populations of fish, mussels, snails and crayfishes. This information may remain blank if you are not surveying within a SHU.

Crossing ID's should be acquired from the Service, Alabama Ecological Service Field office prior to field work. The ID consists of two parts. The first 5 numbers of the ID is the County FIPS code. This is a 5 digit code unique to each county. The second half of the ID is randomly created for each county and consists of 4 digits. The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) created IDs for almost all crossings for every county in the State of Alabama as well as 47 counties surrounding Alabama.

The SC locations were created by intersecting the NHD (National Hydrography Dataset) High HiRes (High Resolution) river data with the 2010 Tiger Line road dataset. The intersect function created 155,000 + crossings in 110 counties. Most of the identified crossings are accurate. Some however may not exist and a few were not mapped in this process.

Note: If you come across a SC that hasn't been given an ID create one by using the closest known crossing ID and add the letter "A". This datasheet can then be submitted to the Alabama Ecological Service office so the newly identified crossing can have an ID assigned to it. Identify it as a **New Crossing** by checking the box in the **New Crossing** field in the datasheet.

If no crossing exists where a Crossing ID was created fill out the Crossing ID, Date, Surveyor(s), and the coordinates on the data sheet. Circle "No" for **Full Survey Performed** and write "Does Not Exist" as the reason.

If two Crossing ID's were created for a single crossing, which can happen for a large crossing like an interstate, pick one of the two ID's for the site survey and fill out a datasheet according to the directions for a site the does not exist for the other Crossing ID. For divided highways and interstates, if there is one culvert connecting both lanes, this is considered one crossing. If each lane has its own culvert or bridge, this is considered two crossings.

A full survey is not needed for every crossing on the landscape. Do not complete a full survey at crossings for private driveways (unless permission is granted and it is at a perennial stream (flows continuously all year)), storm relief structures, ephemeral streams (flows only in direct response to precipitation), highway overpasses, or rail road overpasses. This is a judgment call on your part while in the field. If the crossing is at a perennial stream or wetland complete a full survey. Full surveys should also be completed for all bridges on state highways and interstates, if safe conditions allow.

Date and **Survey Start** and **Stop** times are straight forward. Use 24 hour time format. If known, record the **Road Name** as it is labeled on the road itself and include the **Stream Name**.

Include all members of the **Survey** team and note who's **equipment** was used as well as who took the notes. If the data is not logged into the database by the **Note Taker**, the individual loading the data may need to contact the note taker to clarify information.

Indicate if the site is located in the **Upland** part of the state (above the Fall Line) or in the **Lowland** part of the state (below the Fall Line) by circling the correct box.

State should be abbreviated to the standard two letters and record the full **County** name. **Latitude** and **Longitude** should be in Decimal Degrees and the GPS should be set to NAD 83 Datum. Ensure your location data is accurate and complete for other personnel to locate the site easily. GPS coordinates may not be sufficient to locate a previously evaluated site.

Visible Threats are factors that can see from the crossing and road approaches that could threaten the quality of the stream or its ability to pass stream fishes. Check all that apply, record others as necessary, and check the box **No visible threats** if none are observed. Record if the **Road Type** is Paved or Unpaved and if the road is **Public** or **Private**.

Qualitative Sed (Sedimentation) Risk Level is a quick estimate of how much risk there is of sediment influencing the stream. A Low risk level could have no visible stream or road erosion and vegetated road approaches. A High risk level could include eroded banks, road material in the stream, and/or sediment islands in the stream channel.

There may be circumstances where a **Full Survey** cannot be performed due to unsafe conditions, or the SC is on private land, etc. If this is the case, record why the Full Survey was not performed and only complete the Baseline information section of the datasheet.

Remember: Safety First!

Restoration – Project Possibilities is referring to potential projects for restoration at the crossing. Example of projects include: Fencing to keep cattle out of the creek or replacing the culvert due to a fish barrier.

Fill out the **Baseline** portion of the datasheet then take a **photo** of the datasheet (Figure 3.2). For the remainder of the photos follow the “Photopoints” section in the manual (page 37)

FIGURE 3.2. PHOTO OF THE BASELINE PORTION OF THE DATASHEET.

Tip:

By taking a picture of the datasheet with the Baseline portion filled out first you can easily group the photos after you download them. This photo marks the start of the next batch of photos for the crossing identified on the datasheet.

Waterway

Identification of these features relies heavily upon professional judgment and personal experience.

Waterway conditions that are affected by the stream crossing are recorded in this section of the SRI. Identification of these features relies heavily upon professional judgment and personal experience. To decrease survey time, these characteristics are based upon visual observation rather than actual measurements.

Stream Crossing Assessment	5	3	1	Score
WATERWAY				
1. Upstream channel morphology	Least impacted	Moderately impacted	Most impacted	
2. Downstream channel morphology	Least impacted	Moderately impacted	Most impacted	
3. Downstream channel/bank alteration	Natural	Minor or Partial	High	

FIGURE 4.1 WATERWAY SECTION OF THE SRI DATASHEET

Upstream and **Downstream Channel Morphology** score is influenced by the grading scale as described by Rosgen’s (1996) Level 1 stream classification (Appendix B). This system allows for a simplified approach to identifying current stable or unstable channel morphology without the need to identify the source of the impacts or natural pre-existing conditions. This manual presents a short overview of visually classifying stream channels within the context of the SRI. It is not meant to be used as a guide for Rosgen stream classification outside of this SC assessment.

Upstream and **Downstream Channel Morphology** are scored separately within the SRI but classified using identical criteria. Some channel characteristics that are important to classifying streams include streambanks, bankfull stage, floodplain, and channel depth. Refer to Figure 4.2 for a diagram of stream geomorphic characterization.

FIGURE 4.2. LEVEL 1 STREAM CLASSIFICATION (HARRELSON ET AL., 1994)

LEAST-IMPACTED CHANNEL MORPHOLOGY

Stream types and wetlands displaying stable channels that have not been severely impacted by road crossing conditions or other influences are given a score of 5 within the SRI. This category is influenced by the grading scale as described by Rosgen as wetlands or A, B, C, or E streams.

See Figures 5.1 to 5.4 for examples of identifying least-impacted channels.

FIGURE 5.1

EXAMPLE WETLAND. HYDROLOGY OR TOPOGRAPHY MAPS ARE USEFUL EXTERNAL AIDS FOR DIFFERENTIATING BETWEEN WETLAND AND PONDED CHANNELS.

Stream Crossing Assessment				
WATERWAY	5	3	1	Score
1. Upstream channel morphology	Least impacted	Moderately impacted	Most impacted	5
2. Downstream channel morphology	Least impacted	Moderately impacted	Most impacted	
3. Downstream channel/bank alteration	Natural	Minor or Partial	High	

FIGURE 5.3

EXAMPLE ROSGEN C STREAM. NOTE THE WIDE AND SHALLOW SINGLE-THREAD CHANNEL, LOW SINUOSITY, AND LOW ENTRENCHMENT. IN THE CASE OF A DRY CHANNEL SUCH AS THIS, BANKFULL STAGE INDICATORS ARE ESSENTIAL.

FIGURE 5.4

EXAMPLE ROSGEN E STREAM. NOTE THE NARROW AND DEEP SINGLE-THREAD CHANNEL, SINUOSITY, WIDE FLOOD PLAIN, AND LACK OF ENTRENCHMENT. WITHOUT PHYSICAL DATA, THIS CHANNEL COULD ARGUABLY BE CONSIDERED A ROSGEN C STREAM, BUT THIS WOULD NOT CHANGE ITS SCORE.

Suggestion

Avoid spending excess time differentiating between Rosgen C and E streams. These differences have no bearing on the final SRI score.

MODERATELY-IMPACTED CHANNEL MORPHOLOGY

Waterways identified as beaver dammed or displaying incomplete braiding due to high sediment load are given a score of 3 within the SRI. The stream morphology in these cases is considered a transitional state of disequilibrium. This category is influenced by the grading scale as described by Rosgen as beaver dam or DA streams.

See Figures 6.1 and 6.2 for examples of moderately-impacted stream channels.

FIGURE 6.1

EXAMPLE BEAVER DAM. THE PRESENCE OF THE DAM PRECLUDES THE CHANNEL FROM BEING IDENTIFIED AS WETLANDS OR PONDED.

FIGURE 6.2

EXAMPLE ROSGEN DA STREAM. NOTE THE INCOMPLETE BRAIDED NATURE OF THE CHANNEL.

MOST-IMPACTED CHANNEL MORPHOLOGY

Severely degraded waterways that are ponded and stream types possessing incised channels, high streambanks, and excessive bank erosion exacerbated by, or resulting from, road crossings or other influences are given a score of 1 within the SRI. This category is influenced by the grading scale as described by Rosgen as ponded or D, F, or G streams.

See Figures 7.1 to 7.4 for examples of most-impacted stream channels.

FIGURE 7.1

EXAMPLE PONDED SYSTEM. PONDED CHANNELS OFTEN POSSESS DEEP STREAMBEDS ON ONE SIDE OF THE ROAD, AND A DRAINAGE OR STREAM CHANNEL ON THE OTHER SIDE. TYPICALLY, SUCH SCENARIOS ARE ARTIFICIALLY CREATED BY THE PRESENCE OF THE ROAD CROSSING OR LANDOWNER INTERVENTION.

FIGURE 7.2

EXAMPLE ROSGEN D STREAM. NOTE THE MULTI-THREADED CHANNEL TYPICAL OF D STREAMS.

FIGURE 7.3

EXAMPLE ROSGEN F STREAM. NOTE THE HEAVILY ENTRENCHED “U-SHAPE” CHANNEL TYPICAL OF F STREAMS.

FIGURE 7.4

EXAMPLE ROSGEN G STREAM. NOTE THE HEAVILY ENTRENCHED, NARROW GULLY TYPICAL OF G STREAMS.

Suggestion

Avoid spending excess time differentiating between Rosgen F and G streams. These differences have no bearing on the final SRI score.

DOWNSTREAM CHANNEL/BANK ALTERATION

Channel and bank alteration are identified for the downstream channel only within the SRI. Upstream conditions, though important, were found to be statistically irrelevant to the final score.

Natural channels that lack evidence of any alteration to the streambanks, stream meander pattern, or morphology are given a score of 5. See Figure 8.1 for an example of a natural Channel.

FIGURE 8.1

EXAMPLE NATURAL CHANNEL.
NOTE THE RIPARIAN VEGETATION
AND LACK OF ENTRENCHMENT.

Channels with minor or partial alterations, having evidence of recent embankment alteration or dredging, are given a score of 3. See Figure 8.2 for an example of minor channel alteration.

FIGURE 8.2

EXAMPLE MINOR CHANNEL ALTERATION.
NOTE THE SEDIMENT DEPOSITED WITHIN
CLOSE VICINITY OF THE STREAM CROSSING.
THE MAJORITY OF THE CHANNEL REMAINS
RELATIVELY UNAFFECTED.

Streams with highly altered channels are given a score of 1. These streams typically having greater than 80% of the channel modified, lack significant riparian vegetation, or may contain riprap, dam structures, or other human-made alterations. See Figure 8.3 for an example of a Highly altered stream channel.

FIGURE 8.3

EXAMPLE HIGHLY ALTERED CHANNEL. NOTE THE CATTLE TRACKS, FENCING STRUCTURES, AND LACK OF A DEFINED, STABLE CHANNEL MORPHOLOGY.

Suggestion

Look for a highly incised channel and/or the lack of significant streambank vegetation as strong indicators of a highly altered stream.

CLASSIFYING DRY CHANNELS

The lack of water in a stream channel should not exclude a SC from an SRI assessment. Perennial, ephemeral, and drought-affected streams, however, can be difficult to characterize. Data collectors must rely on visual indicators of pre-existing waterway features, such as bankfull stage, riparian corridor, floodplains, streambed scouring and riffles, and vegetation. Due to the brevity of this guide, only examples of bankfull stage indicators, the point at which the water channel meets the floodplain, will be provided. As a general rule, metrics that still cannot be applied to a dry channel are given a score of 5.

FIGURE 9.1 EXAMPLE DRY CHANNEL DEPICTING BANKFULL STAGE INDICATORS. THE BANKFULL STAGE (B) MAY OFTEN EXIST AT THE TRANSITION OF A STEEP BANK SLOPE TO A GENTLE SLOPE. THIS SUDDEN CHANGE IN THE STREAMBANK OFTEN LEADS DIRECTLY INTO THE FLOODPLAIN (A).

FIGURE 9.2

EXAMPLE DRY CHANNEL DEPICTING BANKFULL STAGE INDICATORS. THE LOWEST EXTENT OF WOODY VEGETATION OFTEN INDICATES THE BANKFULL STAGE (A). A DISTINCT CHANGE IN NON-WOODY VEGETATION MAY ALSO BE AN INDICATOR.

FIGURE 9.3 EXAMPLE PERENNIAL CHANNEL DEPICTING BANKFULL STAGE INDICATORS. THE BANKFULL STAGE (B) MAY OFTEN EXIST AT A TRANSITION OF VEGETATION (B) OR AT THE TOP OF A POINT BAR (C). THE NEARLY FLAT TOP OF A DEVELOPING POINT BAR LEADS TO THE FLOODPLAIN (A).

COMPLETING THE WATERWAY SURVEY

Once the **Waterway** section of the SRI is completed, sum the three scores (1, 3, or 5) for each metric to determine **Waterway** score. See Figure 10.1 for an example of scoring.

Stream Crossing Assessment				
WATERWAY	5	3	1	Score
1. Upstream channel morphology	Least impacted	Moderately impacted	Most impacted	1
2. Downstream channel morphology	Least impacted	Moderately impacted	Most impacted	5
3. Downstream channel/bank alteration	Natural	Minor or Partial	High	3

TOTAL 9

FIGURE 10.1 EXAMPLE DATASHEET RECORDING THE WATERWAY SECTION. THE TOTAL WATERWAY SCORE WAS 9 (1+5+3).

Crossing Structure

Though structural dimensions do not factor into the SRI score, they are important in developing Best Management Practices (BMPs) and identifying fish passage barriers associated with the SC.

The **Crossing Structure** section of the SRI deals with the physical qualities and conditions of culverts, bridges, and fords that are present at a SC, as well as the physical integrity of supporting and adjacent features. A tape measure and compass may be needed for recording structural dimensions.

CROSSING STRUCTURE	BIN Number:			TOTAL:	
Crossing type: Culvert Bridge Ford	Number of culverts:			Bat Signs Present: <input type="checkbox"/>	
Culvert type (circle all that apply): Round Pipe elliptical Open arch Box Trough box Open box Other:					
Structure materials (circle all that apply):	Corrugated metal	PVC	Synthetic	Reinforced concrete	
	Wood	Other metal	Native soil	Clay	Rock Other:
Dimensions:	Length/Span (ft):	Diameter/Width (ft):		Culvert outfall drop (ft):	
		5	3	1	Score
4. Upstream culvert skew angle (worst):	< 5°		5° to 30°		> 30°
5. Crossing fill condition (dominant)	Good Vegetated		Fair Riprap		Poor Bare soil
6. Crossing inlet/outlet condition:	No impairment		Sediment islands Scouring		Blocked
Comments:					TOTAL:

FIGURE 11.1 CROSSING STRUCTURE SECTION OF THE INCLUDED SRI DATASHEET

Within the **Crossing Structure** section of the SRI, identify the type of crossing structure - culvert, bridge, or ford. If the crossing is a bridge and a Bridge Identification Number (BIN) is found written on the bridge, record the number in the **BIN Number** box. This number can be on the inside or outside of the bridge and may be spray painted. If the crossing is a culvert (s), record the **Number of culverts**.

Within **Crossing Structure** section is an option to record **Bat Signs Present**. Bat signs include: seeing a bat or bats, hearing a bat or bats, staining of the bats' entry and exit point, or seeing guano (bat droppings). Check the box if one or more of these signs were observed. If no signs were observed leave the box blank. Use the notes section to write in additional information if needed.

Include all structures present for those SCs that possess more than one type of crossing structure. For culverts, the **Culvert Type** should be noted; ignore this descriptor for bridges and fords. For all crossing structures, note the **Structure Materials**; more than one material may be applicable. For fords, or low-water crossings, use the streambed material on the road approach as the structure material. See Figures 11.2 to 11.8 for examples of crossing structures, types, and materials.

FIGURE 11.2 EXAMPLE FORD. FORDS ARE OFTEN REFERRED TO AS LOW-WATER CROSSINGS, AS SHALLOW WATER IS ALLOWED TO FLOW DIRECTLY ACROSS THE ROAD APPROACH OVER SOIL, CLAY AND/OR ROCK.

**FIGURE 11.3
EXAMPLE WOOD BRIDGE**

FIGURE 11.4 EXAMPLE REINFORCED CONCRETE BRIDGE. THE FOUNDATION PILES OR POLES (A) DISTINGUISH THIS CONCRETE BRIDGE FROM A CONCRETE DOUBLE OPEN-BOX CULVERT.

FIGURE 11.5 EXAMPLE CONCRETE DOUBLE OPEN BOX CULVERT. THE CAST CONCRETE WALL (A) DISTINGUISHES THIS DOUBLE BOX CULVERT FROM A CONCRETE BRIDGE.

FIGURE 11.6 . EXAMPLE TRIPLE BOX CULVERT. THE LACK OF A CONCRETE OR ARTIFICIAL FLOOR IDENTIFIES A BOX CULVERT AS OPEN. HOWEVER, STREAMBED MATERIAL OR VEGETATION MAY DEPOSIT AND CONCEAL THIS INDICATOR (A).

FIGURE 11.7 EXAMPLE CORRUGATED METAL PIPE CULVERT WITH WOOD HEADWALL

FIGURE 11.8 EXAMPLE CONCRETE PIPE CULVERT

MEASURING CROSSING STRUCTURE DIMENSIONS

Though structural dimensions do not factor into the SRI score, they are important in developing BMPs and identifying fish passage barriers associated with the SC.

When measuring the **Dimensions** of a bridge or box culvert, the length is equal to the distance parallel to the road, at the junctions of the road approach and the bridge structural material. Note that road surface material may have accumulated as deck cover and conceal the structural material. The width of a bridge or box culvert is equal to the distance from each lip perpendicular to the road approach.

FIGURE 12.1 HOW TO MEASURE LENGTH/SPAN OF A BRIDGE OR BOX CULVERT.

FIGURE 12.2. HOW TO MEASURE DIAMETER/WIDTH OF A BRIDGE OR BOX CULVERT.

When measuring the Dimensions of a pipe or open arch culvert, the span is equal to the distance between culvert openings, and the diameter is equal to the width of the opening itself. Measure the diameter of the culvert opening, or one of the culverts if there are multiple, and record the value on the sheet.

FIGURE 12.3. HOW TO MEASURE LENGTH/SPAN OF A PIPE OR OPEN ARCH CULVERT.

FIGURE 12.4. HOW TO MEASURE DIAMETER/WIDTH OF A PIPE OR OPEN ARCH CULVERT.

The **Culvert Outfall Drop** is the height from the water surface to the floor of a perched culvert (See Figure 12.5). If the channel is dry, measure the height from the streambed to the floor of the culvert. If the culvert is not perched or is embedded, leave the field blank or zero.

FIGURE 12.5
EXAMPLE PERCHED CULVERT AND MEASURED OUTFALL DROP (A).

SCORING CROSSING CONDITIONS

The **Upstream Culvert Skew Angle** is the degree of misalignment between the span of a culvert and the direction of flow into the culvert. Improperly aligned culverts can disturb stream flow, increase turbulence, and exacerbate scouring and erosion. Culverts with an angle offset from the stream channel by greater than 30 degrees are scored a 1 in the SRI. Angles between 5 to 30 degrees are given a score of 3, and those culverts having less than a 5 degree angle are given a score of 5. See Figures 13.1 to 13.4 for examples of culvert skew angles. For sites with multiple culverts where the majority of the flow (thalweg) is concentrated into one culvert, use the largest or worst skew angle for scoring. Bridges and fords that do not possess secondary culverts are given a score of 5 for this metric.

FIGURE 13.1 EXAMPLES OF UPSTREAM CULVERT SKEW ANGLES. AN ANGLE OF 39° (A) IS SCORED A 1. AN ANGLE OF 14° (B) IS SCORED A 3. AN ANGLE OF 0°(C) IS SCORED A 5.1

FIGURE 13.2
EXAMPLE UPSTREAM CULVERT SKEW ANGLE. THIS 55° ANGLE IS SCORED A 1 IN THE SRI.

Suggestion When scoring this metric, ignore downstream flow completely and upstream flow beyond 50 feet from the stream crossing. With meandering channels, use the closet riffle or run forward of the channel bend.

FIGURE 13.3

EXAMPLE UPSTREAM CULVERT SKEW ANGLE. THIS 24° ANGLE IS SCORED A 3 IN THE SRI. NOTE THAT THE CLOSEST RUN FORWARD OF THE STREAM BEND IS USED AS UPSTREAM FLOW.

FIGURE 13.4 EXAMPLE UPSTREAM CULVERT SKEW ANGLE. THE LACK OF AN OFFSET ANGLE IS SCORED A 5 IN THE SRI AND IS TYPICAL OF PONDED WATERWAYS AND WETLANDS.

The **Crossing Fill Condition** characterizes the fill material encompassing and/or supporting the crossing structure(s). For culverts, the fill material will surround the structure completely or overlay the headwall. For bridges and many box culverts, fill material lies predominantly over the wingwalls and abutments. Do not include the primary road surface as part of the crossing fill, but rather that material within the ditch boundaries or edges of the road approach. Fords, or low-water crossings, lack crossing fill and are given a score of 5 for this metric.

Good crossing fill conditions are scored a 5 within the SRI and do not show signs of erosion and are well vegetated. Fair crossing fill conditions are scored a 3 and show signs of erosion, riprap, geotextile material, and/or incomplete vegetation. Poor crossing fill conditions are scored a 1 and are indicated by lack of vegetation, concreted, bare soil, severe erosion, or undercutting of the crossing structure. When multiple fill conditions are present, use the most prevalent condition identified. See Figures 14.1 to 14.3 for examples of crossing fill conditions.

FIGURE 14.1 EXAMPLE GOOD CROSSING FILL CONDITION (SCORED 5). FOR THIS BOX CULVERT, THE CROSSING FILL MATERIAL LIES PREDOMINANTLY OVER THE WINGWALLS (A).

FIGURE 14.2 EXAMPLE FAIR CROSSING FILL CONDITION (SCORED 3). NOTE THE PARTIAL VEGETATION, LACK OF SEVERE EROSION, AND POORLY MAINTAINED RIPRAP.

FIGURE 14.3 EXAMPLE POOR CROSSING FILL CONDITION (SCORED 1). NOTE THE SEVERE EROSION, BARE SOIL, AND UNDERCUTTING OF THE CROSSING STRUCTURE.

The **Crossing Inlet/Outlet Condition** characterizes specific impacts of the crossing structure within immediate reach of both upstream and downstream openings. Stream crossing structures that are impaired or blocked (80% or greater of stream flow reduction) are given a score of 1 within the SRI. Impairment may be due to collapse or failure of the crossing structure, accumulated debris, or improper installation. Crossing inlet/outlets with sediment islands and/or crossing-induced scouring are given a score of 3 if minor or no stream flow reduction is present. Crossing structures with little to no stream flow reduction are given a score of 5 within the SRI. If the SC contains multiple crossing structures, score the site based on the worst condition present. See Figures 15.1 to 15.3 for examples of inlet/outlet conditions.

FIGURE 15.1
EXAMPLE CROSSING INLET/OUTLET
CONDITION (SCORED 1). NOTE THE
DEBRIS, COLLAPSED CONCRETE
CULVERT,
AND LACK OF SIGNIFICANT
STREAM
FLOW.

FIGURE 15.2 EXAMPLE CROSSING INLET/OUTLET CONDITIONS (SCORED 3). SCOUR POOLS ARE OFTEN CREATED BY CULVERTS AND EXACERBATED BY OUTFALL DROPS (LEFT). EXCESSIVE SEDIMENT MAY BE TRANSPORTED INTO THE STREAM AND ACCUMULATE INTO SEDIMENT ISLANDS (RIGHT).

FIGURE 15.3 EXAMPLE CROSSING INLET/OUTLET CONDITIONS (SCORED 5). NOTE THE LACK OF IMPAIRMENT, CROSSING-INDUCED SCOURING, OR SEDIMENT ISLANDS. THOUGH THERE IS EVIDENCE OF SILT DEPOSITION, IT DOES NOT AFFECT THIS METRIC SCORE.

COMPLETING THE CROSSING STRUCTURE SURVEY

Once the **Crossing Structure** section of the SRI is completed, sum the three scores (1, 3, or 5) for each metric to determine the Crossing Structure score. See Figures 16.1 and 16.2 for an example of scoring.

FIGURE 16.1 EXAMPLE CROSSING STRUCTURE USED FOR SCORING IN FIGURE 16.2.

CROSSING STRUCTURE		BIN Number:		TOTAL:	
Crossing type: Culvert Bridge Ford		Number of culverts: 1		Bat Signs Present: <input type="checkbox"/>	
Culvert type (circle all that apply): Round Pipe elliptical Open arch Box Trough box Open box Other:					
Structure materials: Corrugated metal PVC Synthetic Reinforced concrete					
(circle all that apply): Wood Other metal Native soil Clay Rock Other:					
Dimensions:		Length/Span (ft): 20	Diameter/Width (ft): 1.25	Culvert outfall drop (ft): 0	
		5	3	1	Score
4. Upstream culvert skew angle (worst):		< 5°	5° to 30°	> 30°	5
5. Crossing fill condition (dominant)		Good Vegetated	Fair Riprap	Poor Bare soil	5
6. Crossing inlet/outlet condition:		No impairment	Sediment islands Scouring	Blocked	3
Comments: Chicken wire at US outlet creating scouring					TOTAL: 13

FIGURE 16.2 EXAMPLE DATASHEET RECORDING THE CROSSING STRUCTURE SECTION. REFER TO FIGURE 5.20 FOR THE ASSOCIATED CROSSING STRUCTURE PHOTOGRAPH.

Road Approaches I

References to left and right are oriented with the surveyor facing downstream at the stream crossing.

Do not complete Road Approaches I for Paved Roads. Due to the road being paved and assuming that no road material will be contributing to sedimentation, this section is given an automatic total score of 20.

The **Road Approaches I** section of the SRI deals primarily with quantitative variables of an **Unpaved** road. References to left and right are oriented with the surveyor facing downstream at the stream crossing. A tape measure and clinometer may be needed to record road dimensions.

ROAD APPROACHES I		Right = right road approach when facing downstream						
Dimensions (right):	Length (mi):	Width (ft):	Road prism fill (in):	Slope (%):				
Potential eroded volume (right): Length x Width x Road prism fill x 16.3 =		c.y.						
Dimensions (left):	Length (mi):	Width (ft):	Road prism fill (in):	Slope (%):				
Potential eroded volume (left): Length x Width x Road prism fill x 16.3 =		c.y.						
		5		3		1		Score
		Upland	Lowland	Upland	Lowland	Upland	Lowland	
7. Potential eroded volume (mean)		< 15 c. y.	< 21 c.y.	15-30 c.y.	21-40 c.y.	> 30 c.y.	> 40 c.y.	
8. Soil type:	K-factor:	≤ .15	≤ 0.20	0.16-0.30	0.21-0.40	> .30	> 0.40	
9. Road approach slope (mean %)		≤ 1.5 %	≤ 2.0 %	1.6-3.0 %	2.1-4.0 %	> 3.0%	> 4.0 %	
10. Road approach surface material		All Aggregate or 1 APR: Aggregate 1 APR: Sand/Clay		All Sand/Clay or 1 APR: Aggregate 1 APR: Native Soil		All Native Soil or 1 APR: Native Soil 1 APR: Sand/Clay		
NOTES		TOTAL:						
Use English units only								

FIGURE 17.1 ROAD APPROACHES I SECTION OF THE INCLUDED SRI DATASHEET.

The **Dimensions** of each road approach include the **Length** (in miles), **Width** (in feet), **Road Prism Fill** (in inches), and the **Slope** (as a percentage). Use English units only. If a site is located in an Upland area, apply the Upland scoring criteria. If a site is located in a Lowland area, apply the Lowland scoring criteria (highlighted in gray). See Figure 17.1 for a diagram of road approach dimensions.

The **Length** of a road approach is the distance from the crossing structure to the hydrologic crest, or hilltop at which water runoff flows away from the stream crossing. Do not include the length of a box culvert or bridge with this measurement. This distance is measured in miles with a GPS unit or vehicle odometer.

Suggestion

Avoid measuring road prism fill or road approach width at or near the crossing structure. Exacerbated conditions near the stream crossing may result in skewed data.

The **Width** of a road approach is the trafficked distance between the roadside edges of the ditches; road approach width does not include the width of the road ditches. This distance is measured in feet with a tape measure.

When measuring an **Unpaved Road**: The **Road Prism Fill** is the thickness of loose road fill over the road approach, measured in inches. This is measured by performing a Heel Kick Test. With the heel of your shoe kick three strikes into the road material at two location near the top of the approach. Measure the depth of the heel mark and average the measurements. Record this value on the sheet.

Road approach **Width** and **Road Prism Fill** may each be recorded once at the hydrologic crest or averaged from multiple measurements along the length of the road approach.

The **Slope** of a road approach is the angle of descent or steepness of the road approach to the crossing structure. This angle is measured as a percentage or degree using a clinometer. The

Slope is determined by averaging at least three measurements made along the length of the road approach. On the datasheet record each measurement and the average percent slope.

Slope calculation		PHOTOS	1	Upstream channel from crossing
Right (%)	Left (%)		2	Downstream channel from crossing
1. _____	1. _____		3	Right road approach from crossing
2. _____	2. _____		4	Left road approach from crossing
3. _____	3. _____		5	Crossing structure from upstream
4. _____	4. _____		6	Crossing structure from downstream
5. _____	5. _____		7	Right road approach from 150 ft
Avg. _____	Avg. _____		8	Left road approach from 150 ft
ROAD APPROACHES II		Right = right road approach when facing downstream		

FIGURE 17.2 Record the measurements on the datasheet at the top of page 2 and calculate the average.

The **Potential Eroded Volume** is an estimate of the road prism that may be transported during a rain event based on the surveyed dimensions. The formula provided on the included datasheet (Length x Width x Road Prism Fill x 16.3) is a basic volume formula with a conversion factor (16.3) that provides a result in cubic yards (c.y.). Note that if road approach dimensions are not recorded with the indicated units, this formula must be modified accordingly.

SCORING ROAD APPROACHES I

Complete Road Approaches I scoring in the office once you have computer and internet access. The mean of **Potential Eroded Volumes** for all surveyed road approaches is used to score sediment volume within the SRI. The scoring of potential road surface loss from runoff is a rough estimate standardized statistically and adjusted by professional experience. For fields 7, 8, and 9 in the Road Approach I section, if a site is located in an Upland area, apply the Upland scoring criteria. If a site is located in a Lowland area, apply the Lowland scoring criteria (highlighted in gray). The SRI uses the **Soil Type and K Factors** found in the USDA soil taxonomy found in soil surveys and the USDA Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS) web soil survey (<http://websoilsurvey.nrcs.usda.gov/app/>, accessed January, 2016). When using the NRCS web soil survey, refer to the ratings found under “Soil Data Explorer⇒Soil Properties and Qualities⇒Soil Erosion Factors⇒K Factor, Whole Soil”. This factor K is used to quantify soil particle movement due to water and has a role in the Universal Soil Loss Equation (Wischmeier and Smith, 1978). An area-weighted average of the **K Factor** is calculated for all road approaches involving multiple soil types following the protocol used by the Ohio Environmental Protection Agency (2002). Multiple road approaches may be averaged after their area-weighted factors are calculated, or a single area-weighted average may be used of the entire surveyed area. Soil **K Factors** scores were derived from Manrique, 1988.

The mean **Slope** of surveyed road approaches is calculated using the percent slopes. The combination of **Road Approach Surface Material** is identified for each approach (AP) or all approaches. Native soil roads are scored a 1 and have a high risk for sedimentation. Less erosive native soil types, in these cases, are reflected within the SRI by their **K factor** scores. However, coarser soils typically have the highest risk to detachment than gravel, clay, or amended surfaces (Briggs, 1977; Manrique, 1988). Unpaved roads with at least one aggregate amended approach in combination with a native soil approach are given a score of 3; otherwise, the presence of at least one native soil road approach indicates a score of 1 within the SRI. Sand or clay surface road approaches without native soil or aggregate are given a score of 3. Paved roads and aggregate approaches, or a combination of sand/clay and aggregate approaches, are given a score of 5. See Figures 18.1 and 18.2 for examples of **Road Surface Material**.

FIGURE 18.1 TWO ROAD APPROACHES SURVEYED AT AN UNPAVED ROAD STREAM CROSSING. THE COMBINATION OF CLAY SURFACE MATERIAL (LEFT APPROACH) AND AGGREGATE AMENDED ROAD SURFACE (RIGHT APPROACH) IS GIVEN A SCORE OF 5.

FIGURE 18.2 TWO ROAD APPROACHES SURVEYED AT AN UNPAVED ROAD STREAM CROSSING. THE COMBINATION OF NATIVE SOIL MATERIAL (LEFT APPROACH) AND CLAY ROAD SURFACE (RIGHT APPROACH) IS GIVEN A SCORE OF 1.

COMPLETING THE ROAD APPROACHES I SURVEY

Once the **Road Approaches I** section of the SRI is completed, sum the three scores (1, 3, or 5) for each metric to determine the **Road Approaches I** score. See Figure 19.1 for an example of scoring.

ROAD APPROACHES I		Right = right road approach when facing downstream					
Dimensions (right):	Length (mi): 0.25	Width (ft): 25.5	Road prism fill (in): 2	Slope (%): 4			
Potential eroded volume (right): Length x Width x Road prism fill x 16.3 = _____ c.y.							
Dimensions (left):	Length (mi): 0.36	Width (ft): 24	Road prism fill (in): 2	Slope (%): 7			
Potential eroded volume (left): Length x Width x Road prism fill x 16.3 = 399 c.y.							
		5		3		1	Score
		Upland	Lowland	Upland	Lowland	Upland	Lowland
7. Potential eroded volume (mean) 303.4	< 15 c. y.	< 21 c.y.	15-30 c.y.	21-40 c.y.	> 30 c.y.	> 40 c.y.	1
8. Soil type: CbE3 K-factor: 0.28	≤ .15	≤ 0.20	0.16-0.30	0.21-0.40	.30	> 0.40	3
9. Road approach slope (mean %) 5.5	≤ 1.5 %	≤ 2.0 %	1.6-3.0 %	2.1-4.0 %	> 3.0%	> 4.0 %	1
10. Road approach surface material	All Aggregate or 1 APR: Aggregate 1 APR: Sand/Clay		All Sand/Clay or 1 APR: Aggregate 1 APR: Native Soil		All Native Soil or 1 APR: Native Soil 1 APR: Sand/Clay		5
TOTAL:							10
NOTES							
Use English units only							

FIGURE 19.1 EXAMPLE DATASHEET RECORDING THE ROAD APPROACHES I SECTION.

Photopoints

Photopoints should be established at the time the SC was surveyed.

The Photopoints section of the SRI is an inventory of photographs taken at the evaluated SC. The photographs are to be taken in the same order at every SC. If you are unable to take one of

the 8 photographs at a site it may be skipped but noted on the data sheet. Safety and private property access are two of the main reasons pictures are unable to be taken.

Set your camera to take photographs at low to mid quality. This will keep the file size from getting too large.

The first photo is of the **Baseline** portion of the datasheet, as described on page 7. Proceed taking the 8 field pictures in the order listed in the **Photos** section of the SRI datasheet. The

FIGURE 20.1. PHOTO OF THE DATASHEET WITH THE BASELINE INFORMATION FILLED OUT.

photo section is on the second page in the top right corner.

Check off the photo's as you take them and remember to note any that were not taken.

PHOTOS	1	Upstream channel from crossing	
	2	Downstream channel from crossing	
	3	Right road approach from crossing	
	4	Left road approach from crossing	
	5	Crossing structure from upstream	
	6	Crossing structure from downstream	
	7	Right road approach from 150 ft	
	8	Left road approach from 150 ft	

Figure 20.2 PHOTOS SECTION OF THE SRI DATASHEET

Reminder
 When facing downstream the Right Road Approach will be to your right.

FIGURE 20.3 DRAWING SHOWING ROAD APPROACH IN RELATION TO UPSTREAM AND DOWNSTREAM DIRECTION.

EXAMPLE OF PHOTOS NEEDED FOR THE SRI DATASHEET

Road Approaches II

These metrics rely primarily on professional judgment of improved outlet and drainage systems.

The **Road Approaches II** section of the SRI deals primarily with qualitative variables of the road. References to left and right are oriented with the surveyor facing downstream at the stream crossing. These metrics rely primarily on professional judgment of improved outlet and drainage systems.

ROAD APPROACHES II		Right = right road approach when facing downstream									
DOWNSTREAM											
Left outlet	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right outlet	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1		
(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0	(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		
Left ditch	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right ditch	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1		
(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0	(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		
UPSTREAM											
Left outlet	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right outlet	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1		
(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0	(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		
Left ditch	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right ditch	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1		
(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0	(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		
OUTLET SUM:					DITCH SUM:						
				If SUM = 4,2, or 0, then add	+1					If SUM = 4,2, or 0, then add	+1
				If SUM = 1, then add	+2					If SUM = 1, then add	+2
				If SUM = 3, then add	+0					If SUM = 3, then add	+0
11. Outlet TOTAL					12. Ditch TOTAL						

FIGURE 21.1 ROAD APPROACHES II SECTION OF THE INCLUDED SRI DATASHEET. U/S REFERS TO UPSTREAM OF THE CROSSING STRUCTURE AND D/S REFERS TO DOWNSTREAM OF THE CROSSING STRUCTURE.

The **Outlet Systems** (upstream and downstream, left outlet and right outlet) connect the road approaches to the receiving stream channel, ideally in a non-erosive manner. Sediment delivery abatement features at outlets can include vegetation, riprap, armoring, and energy dissipation by sheet flow. Outlets are given a sub-score based on the dominant abatement feature present. See Figures 21.2 to 21.7 for examples of scoring improved and unimproved outlet systems.

FIGURE 21.2. UPSTREAM OUTLET SYSTEM. IN THIS CASE, THE RIGHT UPSTREAM OUTLET IS NOT A WELL-DEFINED DITCH BUT A SHEET AREA OVER VEGETATION.

		UPSTREAM						DOWNSTREAM			
Left outlet (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right outlet (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1		
	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		
Left ditch (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right ditch (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1		
	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		

FIGURE 21.3

SCORING THE OUTLET SYSTEM IN FIGURE 21.3 ABOVE. IN THIS CASE, BOTH UPSTREAM OUTLETS ARE VEGETATED AND A SUB-SCORE OF +1 IS GIVEN TO EACH OUTLET.

FIGURE 21.4 DOWNSTREAM OUTLET SYSTEM. IN THIS CASE, THE OUTLETS FORM SHEET EROSION AND GULLIES OVER BARE SOIL RATHER THAN TRAVEL THROUGH THE VEGETATION.

Suggestion

Often, no direct outlet channel connects the roadside ditches to the stream. In such cases, runoff may spill directly over the stream crossing. This spill area would be the outlet system.

FIGURE 21.5 DOWNSTREAM OUTLET SYSTEM. IN THIS CASE, BOTH OUTLETS CONTAIN CHANNELS WITH RIPRAP AS THEIR PRIMARY SEDIMENT ABATEMENT FEATURE.

ROAD APPROACHES II		Right = right road approach when facing downstream							
DOWNSTREAM									
Left outlet (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right outlet (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1
	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0
Left ditch (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right ditch (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1
	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0
UPSTREAM									
Left outlet (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right outlet (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1
	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0
Left ditch (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right ditch (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1
	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0
OUTLET SUM:					DITCH SUM:				
If SUM = 4,2, or 0, then add				+1	If SUM = 4,2, or 0, then add				+1
If SUM = 1, then add				+2	If SUM = 1, then add				+2
If SUM = 3, then add				+0	If SUM = 3, then add				+0
11. Outlet TOTAL					12. Ditch TOTAL				

FIGURE 21.6

SCORING THE OUTLET SYSTEM IN FIGURE 21.6 ABOVE. THE LEFT DOWNSTREAM OUTLET IS BARE SOIL, RECEIVING A SUB-SCORE OF +0. THE RIGHT DOWNSTREAM OUTLET HAS RIPRAP, RECEIVING A SUB-SCORE OF +1.

To determine the score for the **Outlet System**, sum the sub-scores awarded for each outlet. Then apply the conditional “if-then” statements provided on the datasheet. If the sum of the sub-scores is equal to 4, 2, or 0, then add 1 to the sub-score to determine the SRI score. If the sum of the sub-scores is equal to 1, add 2 to the sub-score to determine the SRI score. If the sum of the sub-scores is equal to 3, then add 0; the sub-score is equal to the SRI score. See Figure 21.7 for an example of completing the **Outlet System** score.

ROAD APPROACHES II		Right = right road approach when facing downstream							
DOWNSTREAM									
Left outlet (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right outlet (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1
	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0
Left ditch (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right ditch (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1
	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0
UPSTREAM									
Left outlet (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right outlet (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1
	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0
Left ditch (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right ditch (pick one):	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1
	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0
OUTLET SUM:					DITCH SUM:				
If SUM = 4,2, or 0, then add				+1	If SUM = 4,2, or 0, then add				+1
If SUM = 1, then add				+2	If SUM = 1, then add				+2
If SUM = 3, then add				+0	If SUM = 3, then add				+0
11. Outlet TOTAL				3	12. Ditch TOTAL				

FIGURE 21.7

SCORING THE OUTLET SYSTEM. THE IMPROVED OUTLET SYSTEM SRI SCORE IS FOUND BY FIRST SUMMING THE SUB-SCORES OF EACH OUTLET (1+1+1+0=3). THEN APPLYING THE IF-THEN STATEMENTS, THE SUM = 3 SO ADD 0 (3+0=3). THE SRI SCORE IS 3. HAD THE SUB-SCORE BEEN 2 THE SRI SCORE WOULD HAVE BEEN 3 (2+1=3) ALSO, IF ALL OUTLETS WERE VEGETATED, THE SRI SCORE WOULD BE 5 (SUM OF 1+1+1+1=4, THEN 4+1=5).

The **Ditch Systems** (upstream and downstream, left ditch and right ditch) transport runoff along the road approach into a drainage outlet toward a stream or water body. Improved ditch systems dissipate the energy of water flow and direct it towards an improved discharge point.

Sediment control features that may be found along ditches can include, but are not limited to, ditch berms, turnouts, armoring, riprap, hay bales, silt fences, and holding ponds. When scoring the **Ditch System**, follow the same guidelines as shown previously for the **Outlet System**. The presence of at least one sediment abatement feature indicates the sub-score awarded for a particular ditch. For example, a ditch with only one riprap check dam along a quarter mile of bare soil would be given a sub-score of +1. See Figures 22.1 and 22.2 for examples of drainage systems.

FIGURE 22.1 DRAINAGE SYSTEM. BARE SOIL DITCHES (LEFT) RECEIVE A SUB-SCORE OF 0, AND VEGETATED DITCHES (RIGHT) RECEIVE A SUB-SCORE OF +1.

FIGURE 22.2 DRAINAGE SYSTEM. RIPRAP IN DRAINAGE DITCHES (LEFT) RECEIVES A SUB-SCORE OF +1, AND VEGETATED SHEET FLOW (RIGHT) RECEIVES A SUB-SCORE OF +1.

SRI Score

The total SRI score and narrative risk may subsequently be used for site prioritization, monitoring, and/or watershed assessment.

The **Sedimentation Risk Index** produces single final score of the surveyed SC by summing the 4 totals found on the SRI datasheet: Waterway, Crossing Structure, Road Approaches I, and Road Approaches II. This final score can range from 12 to 60 and is organized into narrative categories in a three-tier system of low risk, moderate risk, and high risk. Sites that score 46 or greater are considered “low risk” and least impacted due to sedimentation. Sites that score from 37-45 are considered “moderate risk”, and scores 36 or lower are considered “high risk”. The total SRI score and narrative rank may subsequently be used for site prioritization, monitoring, and/or watershed assessment.

At the bottom of page 2 is a space for notes and drawing of the road and stream crossing. Although not required, add notable features about the crossing or the stream that may be important. Within this space is a signature block. Once the datasheet is finished and before the crew leaves the site, the crew member that did not take notes should review the datasheet for accuracy and verify all possible data has been collected. Once the datasheet has been reviewed that person should sign their name.

NOTES
Use English units only
Signature

FIGURE 23.1. ROAD-STREAM CROSSING DRAWING WHERE NOTABLE FEATURES CAN BE DRAWN.

LITERATURE CITED

- Briggs, D., 1977. Soils. Butterworths, London, United Kingdom, 192 pp. CPYRWMA (Choctawhatchee, Pea, and Yellow Rivers Watershed Management Authority), 2000. A Guideline for Maintenance and Service of Unpaved Roads. CPYRWMA, Troy, Alabama, 69 pp.
- Harrelson, C.C., C.L., Rawlins, and J.P. Potyondy, 1994. Stream Channel Reference Sites: An Illustrated Guide to Field Technique. General Technical Report RM-245. Fort Collins, Colorado: U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Forest and Range Experiment Station.
- Manrique, L.A., 1988. Land Erodibility Assessment Methodology –LEAM, Using Soil Survey Data, Based on Soil Taxonomy. University of Hawaii, Editorial and Publication Shop, Honolulu, Hawaii, 28 pp.
- Morris, C.C., P.M. Stewart, and T.P. Simon, 2007. Development of an Index of Biotic Integrity for a Southeastern Coastal Plain Watershed, USA. *Journal of the American Water Resources Association* 43:1-13.
- Ohio Environmental Protection Agency, 2002. Development of Watershed Loading Model for the Sugar Creek Basin. In: Total Maximum Daily Loads for the Sugar Creek Basin. Ohio EPA Division of Surface Water, Columbus, Ohio, 82 pp.
- Rosgen, D., 1996. Applied River Morphology. Wildland Hydrology Books, Pagosa Springs, 390 pp.
- Stewart, P.M., M.M. Pilarczyk, and T.P. Simon, 2006. Development of an Activity Trap Macroinvertebrate Index of Biotic Integrity for Lake Michigan Coastal Wetlands. In: Coastal Wetlands of the Laurentian Great Lakes: Health, Habitat, and Indicators, T.P. Simon and P.M. Stewart (Editors). Author House, Bloomington, Indiana, pp. 321-332.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, 2005. Northwest Florida Unpaved Road-Stream Crossing Manual. U.S. Department of the Interior, Panama City, Florida, pp. 426
- Wischmeier, W.H. and D.D. Smith, 1978. Predicting Rainfall Erosion Losses. Agricultural Research Service, U.S. Department of Agriculture, Agricultural Handbook 537, Washington, D.C.
- Witmer, P.L., P.M. Stewart, and C.K. Metcalf, 2009. Development and Use of a Sedimentation Risk Index for Unpaved Road-Stream Crossings in the Choctawhatchee Watershed. *Journal of the American Water Resources Association* 45(3):734-747.

APPENDIX A. SRI DATA SHEET

Stream Crossing Evaluation Sheet Version 10 Revised 09/30/2021

BASELINE INFORMATION					
SHU Name:		SHU #:		Visible Threats (check all that apply)	
Crossing ID: (FIPS# - Crossing #) _____				Livestock access <input type="checkbox"/>	
Date:		Time 24hr: Start _____ End _____		Eroding banks <input type="checkbox"/>	
Road Name:			Upland		Fish barriers <input type="checkbox"/>
Stream Name:			Lowland		Road material in stream <input type="checkbox"/>
Surveyor(s):			New Crossing? <input type="checkbox"/>		ATV access <input type="checkbox"/>
State: _____ County: _____		Owner of GPS, camera:		No riparian cover <input type="checkbox"/>	
Latitude (DD): _____		Note taker:		No visible threats <input type="checkbox"/>	
Longitude (DD): _____				Others:	
Road Type: Paved <input type="checkbox"/> Unpaved <input type="checkbox"/>		Public <input type="checkbox"/> Private <input type="checkbox"/>		Qualitative Sed Risk Level (circle one): LOW MODERATE HIGH Unsure	
Full Survey Performed? Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> If No, why not? _____				Restoration	
Other Comments: _____				Project Possibility (circle one):	
				Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Maybe <input type="checkbox"/> Unsure <input type="checkbox"/>	
Stream Crossing Assessment					
WATERWAY					
		5		3	
		1		Score	
1. Upstream channel morphology		Least impacted		Moderately impacted	
2. Downstream channel morphology		Least impacted		Moderately impacted	
3. Downstream channel/bank alteration		Natural		Minor or Partial	
CROSSING STRUCTURE					
		BIN Number: _____		TOTAL:	
Crossing type: Culvert <input type="checkbox"/> Bridge <input type="checkbox"/> Ford <input type="checkbox"/>		Number of culverts: _____		Bat Signs Present: <input type="checkbox"/>	
Culvert type (circle all that apply): Round <input type="checkbox"/> Pipe elliptical <input type="checkbox"/> Open arch <input type="checkbox"/> Box <input type="checkbox"/> Trough box <input type="checkbox"/> Open box <input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____					
Structure materials (circle all that apply): Corrugated metal <input type="checkbox"/> PVC <input type="checkbox"/> Synthetic <input type="checkbox"/> Reinforced concrete <input type="checkbox"/> Wood <input type="checkbox"/> Other metal <input type="checkbox"/> Native soil <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Rock <input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____					
Dimensions: Length/Span (ft): _____ Diameter/Width (ft): _____ Culvert outfall drop (ft): _____					
		5		3	
		1		Score	
4. Upstream culvert skew angle (worst):		< 5°		5° to 30°	
5. Crossing fill condition (dominant)		Good Vegetated		Fair Riprap	
6. Crossing inlet/outlet condition:		No impairment		Sediment islands Scouring	
		Blocked			
Comments: _____ TOTAL: _____					
ROAD APPROACHES I					
Right = right road approach when facing downstream					
Dimensions (right): Length (mi): _____ Width (ft): _____ Road prism fill (in): _____ Slope (%): _____ Potential eroded volume (right): Length x Width x Road prism fill x 16.3 = _____ c.y.					
Dimensions (left): Length (mi): _____ Width (ft): _____ Road prism fill (in): _____ Slope (%): _____ Potential eroded volume (left): Length x Width x Road prism fill x 16.3 = _____ c.y.					
		5		3	
		1		Score	
7. Potential eroded volume (mean)		Upland <input type="checkbox"/> Lowland <input type="checkbox"/>		Upland <input type="checkbox"/> Lowland <input type="checkbox"/>	
		< 15 c. y. < 21 c.y.		15-30 c.y. 21-40 c.y.	
8. Soil type: K-factor:		≤ .15 ≤ 0.20		0.16-0.30 0.21-0.40	
9. Road approach slope (mean %)		≤ 1.5 % ≤ 2.0 %		1.6-3.0 % 2.1-4.0 %	
10. Road approach surface material		All Aggregate or 1 APR: Aggregate 1 APR: Sand/Clay		All Sand/Clay or 1 APR: Aggregate 1 APR: Native Soil	
		All Native Soil or 1 APR: Native Soil 1 APR: Sand/Clay			
NOTES					
TOTAL: _____					
Use English units only					

Slope calculation		PHOTOS	*	Completed Baseline info of data sheet							
Right (%)	Left (%)		1	Upstream channel from crossing							
1. _____	1. _____		2	Downstream channel from crossing							
2. _____	2. _____		3	Right road approach from crossing							
3. _____	3. _____		4	Left road approach from crossing							
4. _____	4. _____		5	Crossing structure from upstream							
5. _____	5. _____	6	Crossing structure from downstream								
Avg. _____	Avg. _____	7	Right road approach from 150 ft								
_____	_____	8	Left road approach from 150 ft								
ROAD APPROACHES II		Right = right road approach when facing downstream									
DOWNSTREAM											
Left outlet	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right outlet	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1		
(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0	(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		
Left ditch	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right ditch	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1		
(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0	(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		
UPSTREAM											
Left outlet	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right outlet	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1		
(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0	(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		
Left ditch	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1	Right ditch	Vegetated	Riprap	Synthetic	+1		
(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0	(pick one):	Bare soil	Concrete	Other:	+0		
OUTLET SUM:					DITCH SUM:						
If SUM = 4,2, or 0, then add					If SUM = 4,2, or 0, then add						
If SUM = 1, then add					If SUM = 1, then add						
If SUM = 3, then add					If SUM = 3, then add						
11. Outlet TOTAL					12. Ditch TOTAL						
SEDIMENTATION RISK INDEX (SRI)						TOTAL SRI SCORE:					
Narrative risk rank:		Low risk	Moderate risk	High risk							
SRI score:		46 - 60	37 - 45	12 - 36							
NOTES											
Use English units only											
											Signature

APPENDIX B: ROSGEN STREAM TYPES

APPENDIX C: ROAD ANGLE AND PERCENT SLOPE

Road angle and Percent slope

Angle (°)	Slope (%)										
0.1	0.2	2.6	4.5	6.0	10.5	11	19.4	36	72.7		
0.2	0.4	2.7	4.7	6.2	10.9	12	21.3	37	75.4		
0.3	0.5	2.8	4.9	6.4	11.2	13	23.1	38	78.1		
0.4	0.7	2.9	5.1	6.6	11.6	14	24.9	39	81.0		
0.5	0.9	3.0	5.2	6.8	11.9	15	26.8	40	83.9		
0.6	1.1	3.1	5.4	7.0	12.3	16	28.7	41	86.9		
0.7	1.2	3.2	5.6	7.2	12.6	17	30.6	42	90.0		
0.8	1.4	3.3	5.8	7.4	13.0	18	32.5	43	93.3		
0.9	1.6	3.4	5.9	7.6	13.3	19	34.4	44	96.6		
1.0	1.8	3.5	6.1	7.8	13.7	20	36.4	45	100.0		
1.1	1.9	3.6	6.3	8.0	14.1	21	38.4	46	103.6		
1.2	2.1	3.7	6.5	8.2	14.4	22	40.4	47	107.2		
1.3	2.3	3.8	6.6	8.4	14.8	23	42.5	48	111.1		
1.4	2.4	3.9	6.8	8.6	15.1	24	44.5	49	115.0		
1.5	2.6	4.0	7.0	8.8	15.5	25	46.6	50	119.2		
1.6	2.8	4.1	7.2	9.0	15.8	26	48.8	51	123.5		
1.7	3.0	4.2	7.3	9.2	16.2	27	51.0	52	128.0		
1.8	3.1	4.3	7.5	9.4	16.6	28	53.2	53	132.7		
1.9	3.3	4.4	7.7	9.6	16.9	29	55.4	54	137.6		
2.0	3.5	4.5	7.9	9.8	17.3	30	57.7	55	142.8		
2.1	3.7	4.6	8.1	10.0	17.6	31	60.1	56	148.3		
2.2	3.8	4.7	8.2	10.2	18.0	32	62.5	57	154.0		
2.3	4.0	4.8	8.4	10.4	18.4	33	64.9	58	160.0		
2.4	4.2	4.9	8.6	10.6	18.7	34	67.5	59	166.4		
2.5	4.4	5.0	8.8	10.8	19.1	35	70.0	60	173.2		

APPENDIX D: EQUIPMENT LIST

EQUIPMENT LIST

The following is a recommended list of equipment to for use with the SRI. Though this list is not exhaustive, nor does it consider paperless data collection methods, the equipment presented is sufficient to complete an SRI survey.

Field Equipment

- Pen or Pencil
- Clipboard
- Datasheets
- Maps, GIS software, and/or Site Inventory
- Digital Camera
- GPS unit
- Tape Measure (50' or greater)
- Range Finder and or Survey Wheel
- Clinometer or digital level
- Flashlight (optional)
- Vehicle, with trip marker odometer
- Contact information for survey crews
- High visibility safety vest

Office Equipment

- Soil Survey Maps or NRCS Online Web Soil Survey
- PC or Mac
- Microsoft Access, Excel, or other database entry software